

SITE SPHINX	DATE 17/VIII/80	AREA T (RUMP LEDGE S SIDE)	SQUARE	PAGE
	Coordinates: See 1:50 plan of Rump Ledge and Stonework Section 14		Levels	
			Top:	Bottom:
	DIMENSIONS			
Feature No.	Diameter:	Width: As cleared to "back" 20cm Vertical Fault 5-7cm	Length:	Depth: INTO CORE 10-28 cm

Locus	Mat.	Color	Hard.	Consis.	Pottery	Inclusions	
1	Limestone FRAGS (concentrated); Sand; MORTAR	White (Limestone, Mortar) to Buff (Sand)	LOOSE TO COMPACT (Mortar Compact)	RUBBLY	T 1 very tiny chip	Lm	Sharp frags. * Gp
						Gr	Char ✓ Few Carbon Spots
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	* MORTAR, IRON ORE FRAGS (Very Small - SAMPLED)
** 19.	CLAY (Thin Band)	TAN	COMPACT	FINE	T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
† 2.	SAND	TAN	LOOSE		T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	
○					T	Lm	Gp
						Gr	Char
						Do	
						Ba	
						Al	
						Other	

PHOTOGRAPH	Color: Roll/ No./	B&W: Roll/ No./
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DRAWN	Area Plan: 1:50 of Rump Ledge	Feature Plan:	Sections: See Stonework Section 14
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REMARKS; INTERPRETATION: * Some Limestone frags show red paint-like patina - These sampled.

* This actually a lense
* in characteristic ① fill.

* 1 small greenish faience round flat bead.

† ② Filling narrow (1-2 cm) horizontal fault at bottom.

Td2 a recess in bedrock core behind stonework section 14. Recess characterized by traversing vertical and horizontal faults. Like a fold in the bedrock. Rubble fill taken back 20 cm. from face of section as drawn in section 14